

Prognostic Factors Affecting Nasopharyngeal Carcinoma

Kshitiranjana Das¹, Nandigam Nithin Kumar², Amrita Das³, Sambit Shubham Behera⁴

¹Senior Resident, Department of ENT and Head & Neck Surgery, SCB Medical College and Hospital, Cuttack, Odisha, India

²PG Resident, Department of ENT and Head & Neck Surgery, SCB Medical College and Hospital, Cuttack, Odisha, India

³PG Resident, Department of ENT and Head & Neck Surgery, SCB Medical College and Hospital, Cuttack, Odisha, India

⁴PG Resident, Department of ENT and Head & Neck Surgery, SCB Medical College and Hospital, Cuttack, Odisha, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Sambit Shubham Behera

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Abstract:

This study investigates the impact of clinical stage and Epstein-Barr Virus (EBV) status on survival outcomes in patients with nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC). Encompassing 150 NPC patients from a tertiary care center, the research utilized Kaplan-Meier survival estimates and Cox proportional hazards models to analyze data. Results indicate significant survival discrepancies, with early-stage (I and II) patients exhibiting substantially better 5-year survival rates (85-90%) compared to those diagnosed at later stages (III and IV, 50-65%). Furthermore, EBV-positive patients showed improved survival outcomes (75% survival rate) over EBV-negative counterparts (55%). The findings affirm that both disease stage and EBV status are crucial prognostic indicators, emphasizing the necessity for early detection and the potential for EBV-targeted treatments to enhance patient prognosis in NPC.

Keywords: Nasopharyngeal Carcinoma, Epstein-Barr Virus, Survival Analysis, Prognostic Factors, Cancer Staging.

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Introduction

Nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC) is a distinctive form of cancer that originates from the epithelial cells of the nasopharynx, where the nasal passages and oropharynx converge [1]. Predominantly prevalent in Southeast Asia and North Africa, NPC's unique epidemiological footprint is influenced by a combination of genetic susceptibility, environmental factors, and dietary habits, notably linked with the Epstein-Barr Virus (EBV) infection [2]. This cancer often eludes early diagnosis due to the nasopharynx's complex anatomy and the vague nature of initial symptoms, making the understanding of its prognostic factors critical for effective treatment planning and improving patient outcomes [3].

Several key factors impact the prognosis of NPC: Genetic predispositions are evident, with certain HLA class I alleles significantly more common among NPC patients, suggesting a genetic vulnerability that may interact with environmental factors to heighten cancer risk. The association with EBV is particularly strong in non-keratinizing NPC, where viral DNA levels serve not only as a diagnostic tool but also as a marker for monitoring

treatment response [4]. Environmental and dietary exposures, such as carcinogenic nitrosamines found in salted fish and other factors like wood dust and tobacco smoke, are also critical in influencing NPC incidence [5].

The clinical presentation and staging of NPC are paramount prognostic indicators. The disease's tendency for early lymphatic spread often results in cervical lymph node involvement at diagnosis. Advanced stages marked by significant local invasion and distant metastasis are associated with lower survival rates. Furthermore, the initial therapeutic response, primarily to radiotherapy and chemotherapy, is a crucial predictor of outcomes, with complete responses typically forecasting better survival [6].

This study explores these multifaceted prognostic factors to refine diagnostic techniques, enhance treatment protocols, and improve predictive assessments to boost survival rates and the quality of life for NPC patients. Detailed exploration highlights the necessity for personalized treatment approaches that consider the complex interplay of

genetic, viral, and environmental factors unique to NPC.

Methodology

Study Design: This is an observational cohort study that follows NPC patients to assess various prognostic indicators and their impact on survival and treatment response over a specified period.

Study Population: The study includes patients diagnosed with nasopharyngeal carcinoma at a tertiary care center. Eligible participants are those who have confirmed diagnoses of NPC based on histopathological evaluation and are willing to participate in the study. Patients are excluded if they have received prior treatment for NPC or have other concurrent malignancies that could interfere with the assessment of prognostic factors.

Data Collection: Comprehensive data collection is performed at baseline and during follow-up visits, which occur every three months for the first year and biannually thereafter. The data collected include:

- **Demographic Information:** Age, sex, and socio-economic status.
- **Clinical Data:** Stage at diagnosis (using the TNM staging system), histological type of NPC, presence of EBV DNA, and initial symptoms.
- **Lifestyle Factors:** Dietary habits, exposure to potential environmental carcinogens (like tobacco smoke and wood dust), and a detailed family history of cancers.

- **Treatment Details:** Type of treatment received (radiotherapy, chemotherapy, or combined modalities), doses, and response to treatment.
- **Follow-Up Data:** Disease progression, recurrence, survival status, and cause of death if applicable.

Laboratory Tests: Blood samples are collected to analyze genetic markers and EBV DNA levels. Imaging studies, including MRI and CT scans, are conducted to evaluate the extent of the disease at diagnosis and monitor disease progression or response to treatment.

Statistical Analysis: Data are analyzed using statistical software. Descriptive statistics summarize the demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population. Kaplan-Meier survival curves are used to estimate survival times, and Cox proportional hazards models are employed to assess the impact of various prognostic factors on survival and disease outcomes. Multivariable analysis is used to adjust for potential confounders.

Results

The study enrolled a total of 150 patients diagnosed with NPC. The mean age at diagnosis was 45 years (range: 25-65 years). Most patients were male (60%), reflecting a gender distribution consistent with the known higher incidence of NPC in males. The demographic and clinical characteristics of the patients are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Study Participants

Characteristic	Total Patients (N=150)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	90	60%
Female	60	40%
Age Group		
25-35 years	30	20%
36-45 years	45	30%
46-55 years	50	33.3%
56-65 years	25	16.7%
Stage at Diagnosis		
I	15	10%
II	35	23.3%
III	60	40%
IV	40	26.7%
EBV Status		
Positive	130	86.7%
Negative	20	13.3%

Survival analysis revealed significant differences in outcomes based on the stage at diagnosis and EBV status. The overall 5-year survival rate was 70%, but this varied significantly by stage and EBV

status. Kaplan-Meier survival curves indicated that early-stage patients (stages I and II) had significantly better survival outcomes than those

diagnosed at later stages (III and IV). The survival data are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Kaplan-Meier Estimates of Survival by Stage and EBV Status

Stage/EBV Status	5-Year Survival Rate (%)	Log-rank Test p-value
Stage I	90%	<0.001
Stage II	85%	<0.001
Stage III	65%	<0.001
Stage IV	50%	<0.001
EBV Positive	75%	0.002
EBV Negative	55%	0.002

Cox proportional hazards regression analysis was used to evaluate the independent effects of various prognostic factors on survival. Stage at diagnosis and EBV status remained significant predictors of

survival after adjusting for age, gender, and treatment modalities. The hazard ratios (HRs) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Multivariate Cox Proportional Hazards Model for Survival

Prognostic Factor	Hazard Ratio (HR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Stage III vs. I	2.5	1.5-4.1	<0.001
Stage IV vs. I	3.5	2.1-5.8	<0.001
EBV Negative vs. Positive	1.8	1.1-2.9	0.02

Discussion

The current study found that the stage at diagnosis and EBV status are significant prognostic factors for survival among patients with NPC, aligning with previous research that highlights the pivotal role of these factors in NPC outcomes. Patients diagnosed at an early stage (I or II) demonstrated significantly better survival rates compared to those diagnosed at advanced stages (III or IV), underscoring the critical importance of early detection strategies [7,8].

The strong association of EBV with better survival outcomes, particularly in EBV-positive patients, supports the hypothesis that EBV-related NPC might have a distinct biological behavior compared to EBV-negative tumors. This difference may be attributable to the unique viral oncogenesis pathways, which could be more amenable to targeted therapeutic interventions, such as EBV-specific immunotherapies [9].

The findings of this study are consistent with those reported in the literature. A substantial body of research has established that early-stage NPC is associated with significantly higher survival rates, primarily due to the localized nature of the disease which is amenable to definitive local therapy such as radiation and chemoradiation [10]. Similarly, the

prognostic value of EBV status has been well-documented, with EBV-positive status often associated with a more favorable prognosis, potentially due to the immunogenic nature of viral antigens which may enhance the responsiveness to treatment [11,12].

The results of this study have several implications for clinical practice. Firstly, they reinforce the need for early detection and diagnosis of NPC, which could potentially be facilitated through screening in high-risk populations, particularly in endemic areas [13]. Moreover, the significant role of EBV in prognostic stratification suggests that EBV DNA quantification could be integrated into routine clinical practice not only for diagnostic purposes but also for monitoring disease progression and response to therapy [14].

This study is not without limitations. The observational nature of the study design precludes definitive conclusions about causality. Additionally, while the cohort was adequately sized for detecting significant differences in survival by stage and EBV status, the generalizability of the results may be limited by the single-center study design [15]. Future multicentric studies could provide more robust data and a greater understanding of the impact of regional variations

in genetic, dietary, and environmental factors on NPC outcomes [16].

Future research should focus on prospective studies to confirm these findings and explore the underlying biological mechanisms that contribute to the differences in survival based on EBV status and disease stage. Furthermore, there is a need for clinical trials to evaluate targeted therapies, particularly for advanced-stage and EBV-negative NPC, where outcomes remain suboptimal [17-20].

Conclusion

The study conclusively demonstrates that the stage at diagnosis and Epstein-Barr Virus (EBV) status are pivotal prognostic factors in nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC), significantly influencing patient survival outcomes. Early-stage diagnosis correlates with markedly improved survival rates, underscoring the urgent need for enhanced screening and early detection strategies, particularly in high-risk populations. Additionally, the positive association of EBV status with better outcomes highlights the potential for EBV-targeted therapeutic interventions. These findings advocate for integrating EBV DNA quantification into routine clinical management of NPC to refine prognostic accuracy and tailor treatment approaches, ultimately aiming to improve the prognosis and quality of life for patients afflicted with this challenging cancer.

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